

Ichabod and his remarkable mother

1 Samuel 4:19–22

Part of a longer analysis into the pauses in speech in the Bible

See *A Study in Silence*

Jehovah* had told Samuel (3:11–14):

“Look! I am doing something in Israel which if anyone hears about, both his ears will tingle. 12 On that day I shall carry out toward Eli all that I have said respecting his house, from beginning to end. 13 And you must tell him that I am judging his house to time indefinite for the error that he has known, because his sons are calling down evil upon God, and he has not rebuked them. 14 And that is why I have sworn to the house of Eli that the error of the house of Eli will not be brought to exemption from punishment by sacrifice or by offering to time indefinite.”

That judgement came upon Eli when his two sons, Hophni and Phinehas, were killed in battle (4:11). When Eli was told the news “at the moment that [the messenger] mentioned the [capture of the] ark of the [true] God, [Eli] began to fall from the seat backward beside the gate, and his neck got broken so that he died, because the man was old and heavy” (verse 18). More was to come.

19 And his daughter-in-law, the wife of Phinehas, was pregnant near to giving birth, and she got to hear the report that the ark of the [true] God was captured and that her father-in-law and her husband had died. At that she bowed herself and began giving birth, because her pangs came unexpectedly upon her. 20 And about the time of her death, the women standing by her began to speak: “Do not be afraid, because it is a son that you have borne.” And she did not answer and did not set her heart on it. 21 But she called the boy Ichabod, saying: “Glory has gone away from Israel into exile,” [this] with

* See Appendix, page 6.

reference to the ark of the [true] God's being captured and with reference to her father-in-law and her husband. 22 So she said: "Glory has gone away from Israel into exile, because the ark of the [true] God has been captured."

Birth and death entwine tightly into an intense moment of pain.

Like her father-in-law, the unnamed mother-to-be reacted to the disaster in a similarly startled manner.

The women who attended the birth said, "Do not be afraid [אַל־תִּירָאִי], because it is a son that you have borne". Interestingly, the midwife who attended the birth of Benjamin said something similar to Rachel as she was dying in childbirth: "Do not be afraid [אַל־תִּירָאִי], for you will have this son also" (Genesis 35:17).

Bearing a son was regarded as a supreme blessing. A son meant continuity of the family line, security and inheritance for the household, and honour in a society where childbearing was highly valued. So when the women said "Do not be afraid", they were probably trying to comfort and console and encourage a dying woman. They might have hoped to mean: "Don't despair—you have achieved something wonderful despite your suffering. You will leave behind a son, a hope, a future". It was possibly an attempt to comfort her with what would usually be joyful news. Fokkelman calls their speech "a sign of their powerlessness. It is very difficult in the face of death to say something relevant, personalized, and of value. If someone says "don't be afraid" it may be quite justified, but it can, in some situations, be a signal of something too terrifying to handle" (*Vow*, p. 229).

However, we are told that "she did not answer and did not set her heart on [the words of the women]". In other words, she did not answer the women's attempted good cheer, and she ignored their encouragement. However, she did have something to say, and that tells us why she ignored what the women had said.

The narrator tells us that she called her son אִיכָבֹד, Ichabod, which means "Where is the glory?" (*Insight*, vol. 1, p. 1166). The unnamed mother "is heedless of her own circumstances, neither is she interested in the fact that she has given birth to a male off-spring, and suddenly the cheering-up attempt seems somehow misplaced" (*Vow*, p. 229). The larger catastrophe—the Ark's capture, the death of her husband and father-in-law, and the departure of God's כְּבוֹד, glory, his presence amongst his covenant people—outweighed even the consolation of having a son. Her despair ran deeper than family continuity; she thought that Israel's precious

covenant relationship with God had finished. Family continuity is mentioned only obliquely by the narrator in his explanation of the naming, but only after the greater crisis.

nw translates the connecting ו at the beginning of verse 21 as “But”, which is entirely appropriate since she went on to disagree with the women. Her “personal distress or death are not important and neither is her motherhood even. She uses the birth as a vehicle for transmitting one powerful signal: “I-chabod” (*Vow*, p. 239). At the very moment when she would be all consumed with the birth, her mind was entirely on the theological calamity of Israel.

Here are the two statements either side of what looks like a pause.

21 But she called the boy Ichabod, saying: “Glory has gone away from Israel into exile,” [this] with reference to the ark of the [true] God’s being captured and with reference to her father-in-law and her husband.

22 So she said: “Glory has gone away from Israel into exile, because the ark of the [true] God has been captured.”

m has no punctuation. Patently the first explanation of “Glory has gone away from Israel into exile” was not the woman’s words because she would not have said הַמִּיָּה וְאִישָׁה, “her father-in-law and her husband”.

Here is the repetition:

גָּלָה כְּבוֹד מִיִּשְׂרָאֵל אֶל־הַלְקָח אַרְוֹן הָאֱלֹהִים וְאֶל־חַמִּיָּה וְאִישָׁה
גָּלָה כְּבוֹד מִיִּשְׂרָאֵל בִּי נִלְקַח אַרְוֹן הָאֱלֹהִים

It is possible that the woman only repeated herself, while the explanations are the narrator’s. But there is a difference between the way in which the explanations are introduced. The first is with אֶל, the second with בִּי. It is this difference that suggests that the second explanation is the woman’s. And if that is so, in her dying moment, she seems to take on the narrator’s statement that she was concerned about the death of her father-in-law and her husband. It appears that the death of these two men was eclipsed by the capture and loss of the Ark! That is the only thing *she* wants to mention in her last words, not the high-priest Eli, not her husband Phinehas, but only the Ark. *Insight* (vol.1, p. 166) explains this significance:

The Ark was associated with God’s presence throughout its history. Jehovah promised: “I will present myself to you there and speak with

you from above the cover, from between the two cherubs that are upon the ark of the testimony.” “In a cloud I shall appear over the cover.” (Ex 25:22; Le 16:2) Samuel wrote that Jehovah “is sitting upon the cherubs” (1Sa 4:4); hence the cherubs served as “the representation of the chariot” of Jehovah. (1Ch 28:18)

We know little about this woman. But her emphasis in her final utterance is notable. She was certainly expressing her priority. We only find out that Phinehas had a wife as she was dying. What more do we know about her? Despite being a priest, her husband had no respect for Jehovah (1 Samuel 2:12–17), had called down evil upon God (3:13) and her husband had sex with the women who served at the Tabernacle (2:22). How would she have felt knowing this? Living with such a husband? And knowing that so many others knew?

She was, as Fokkelman says, utterly self-effacing and courageous (*ibid.*, 232). What a contrast to her husband. Her dying words are: “Glory has gone away from Israel into exile” and “Glory has gone away from Israel into exile, because the ark of the [true] God has been captured”. The latter in Hebrew is גְּלוּת כְּבוֹד מִיִּשְׂרָאֵל בִּי נִלְקָחָה, making her last words “the ark of the [true] God”. At the moment she was giving birth and was dying—in the midst of all this pain—her focal point was not on her child and not on her death but on the departure of Jehovah. Just when all her maternal instincts would have been overwhelmingly towards her baby, she was overcome with concern for the covenant and the nation’s relationship with its God, Jehovah.

The gap between these two statements appears to be used by the narrator to highlight this extraordinary utterance of faith, so that the first statement with his explanation is intensified by the second statement. More than that, the narrator allows the woman to reject his claim that she was distressed about the loss of her father-in-law and her husband and to say in effect, No! it’s all about the departure of the Ark. The woman’s two utterances create an exchange with the narrator providing for this escalation of her expression of her faith. You can tell that the narrator is impressed for he honours her with the final words which “provide the crucial definition of the national crisis” (*ibid.*, 231).

In her final statement, by ignoring Eli and Phinehas was she distancing herself from such wicked men? Although she thought that Jehovah had departed, was she putting her future life prospects into his hands?

She teaches us an important lesson. When dominated by personal problems, see the big picture. This is one of the lessons from the book of Job. When under attack from his three companions and from Satan, Job became consumed with his own problems and the unfair criticism directed at him. In his speeches, Jehovah had to redirect Job's focus. When we feel overwhelmed by our trials, observing creation can help us to remember Jehovah's greatness, strengthen our desire to remain loyal to him and build our confidence in his ability to care for us (*mwb24* January p. 7).

APPENDIX

In the Bible the divine name יהוה occurs almost seven thousand times, more often than any of God's titles, and more often than any other separate Hebrew word.

There are many theophoric names in the Bible. The majority of Bible translators transliterate those names which have the first two syllables of the divine name as Jeho. Hence: Jehonathan, Jehoshua, Jehoshaphat, Jehoahaz, Jehonadab, Jehoram etc. When the Israelites shortened a name they would not abbreviate but they contracted it by removing syllables from the middle of the name. So Jehonathan was reduced to Jonathan; Jehoshua became Joshua; Jehonadab became Jonadab. God's name was contracted to Jah, hence: Elijah, Abijah and Hallelujah etc. Therefore, the divine name must have had three syllables, not two.

We believe that a י is more likely to be transliterated as a y in English, and a ו is more likely to be transliterated as a w. So the divine name could be *Yehowah*. However, most Bible scholars avoid any transliteration. They use the tetragrammaton in Hebrew letters יהוה, or they display the divine name as YHWH. This is all well and good, but it is inconsistent with their transliteration of other Bible names. If they are to be consistent then they should either use Yehonathan for Jonathan or show the Hebrew letters יהנתן, or YWNTN. Sometimes they use *Yahweh* which disregards how names were shortened, and it only has two syllables.

The argument that the vowels of יהוה are those of אֱלֹהֵינוּ does not hold up because the vowels are not the same.

Gesenius pointed out that "Those who consider that יהוה was the actual pronunciation [of God's name] are not altogether without ground on which to defend their opinion. In this way can the abbreviated syllables יהו and יו, with which many proper names begin, be more satisfactorily explained."

We believe that *Jehovah* is a reasonable transliteration of the tetragrammaton.

ABBREVIATIONS AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Insight*. *Insight on the Scriptures*, Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania, 2018.
- M Masoretic text found in Codex Leningrad B 19A.
- mwb* *Our Christian Life and Ministry—Meeting Workbook*, Christian Congregation of Jehovah’s Witnesses.
- Vov*. J.P. Fokkelman, *Narrative Art and Poetry in the Books of Samuel, King David*, Volume IV, Van Gorcum, 1993.

Bible quotations are from the *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, 1984 [NW], unless otherwise indicated.